

THE VERB “YATSAR” AS A METAMORPHOSIS OF REALITY IN THE OLD TESTAMENT

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ABSTRACT: The Verb “Yatsar” as a Metamorphosis of Reality in the Old Testament.

The Hebrew verb *yatsar* (יָצַר) means *to form, to shape, to fashion*, and it is frequently used in the Old Testament to describe both human action and God’s act of creation, as well as processes of transformation and the metamorphosis of reality. The question we wish to raise is twofold: 1) To what extent can the meaning of *yatsar* be interchangeable with *bara’*? and 2) Is there a difference between *yatsar* as an action of God and *yatsar*, as a human action? The present research represents an exegetical-theological study, attempting to highlight the meanings of the verb *yatsar* in the context of the Old Testament. Unlike the verb *bara’* (בָּרָא) in Genesis 1, which means *to create* in an absolute sense, *ex nihilo*, *yatsar* implies a process, a work of shaping and perfecting. In the Old Testament, *yatsar* signifies an intentional creation, an act in which God, like a potter, molds man from raw material (dust of the earth). Also, *yatsar* refers to how God intervenes in history, shaping events and transforming reality until the fulfillment of His final plan. Thus, *yatsar* becomes a metaphor for the continuous metamorphosis of reality, a process in which God constantly works to fulfill His divine purposes. By examining all occurrences of the word *yatsar*, we can create a comprehensive picture of the nature of God’s and man’s actions designated by this verb.

Key words: *yatsar, bara’, to create, to form, to shape, ex nihilo, Old Testament.*

Introduction

In the Hebrew Bible, few verbs capture God’s creative dynamism as vividly as יָצַר (*yatsar*), “to form” or “to shape.” Occurring sixty-three times in the Old Testament, the verb carries both material and metaphorical weight.

In *Genesis 2:7-8,19*, it conveys the image of God as a craftsman who fashions the first human being from the dust, endowing him with life through divine breath. This anthropomorphic representation contrasts the transcendent creative aspect of בָּרָא (*bara'*), which introduces existence *ex nihilo*, with the immanent act of *yatsar*, the intimate formation of that which was created. Scholars have long recognized this duality in the biblical conception of creation: God is both transcendent Creator and immanent Shaper. Therefore, the study of *yatsar* provides a hermeneutical key to understanding how the Old Testament describes divine involvement in matter, time, and human consciousness. This research aims to determine whether *yatsar* functions differently in divine and human contexts, and to analyze the semantic overlap and distinction between *yatsar* and *bara'* in the Old Testament context, so that, in conclusion, we may show the implications of humanity being formed (*yatsar*) in the image and likeness of God for the freedom of conscience.

Methodology

This research uses an exegetical-theological and inductive-comparative methodology. The first component focuses on the linguistic and semantic analysis of *yatsar* and related terms, evaluating morphological forms and contextual nuances. The second component examines the comparative occurrences of the terms *yatsar* and *bara'* in parallel biblical contexts, identifying patterns of complementarity or divergence. A third dimension, theological, interprets these findings through the lens of Old Testament theology, seeking to discern what the verbs reveal about the nature of God and the human vocation. The approach is inductive, based on the information provided by the biblical text, but synthetic in theological reflection, correlating the exegetical results with conceptual implications.

Literature Review

The scholarly discussion of *yatsar* has evolved significantly since the late nineteenth century. Early commentators such as John Skinner¹ emphasized the anthropomorphic character of the verb, linking it to the image

1 John Skinner, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on Genesis*, International Critical Commentary (New York: Scribner, 1910), 56.

of the potter (יָצַר, *yōṣēr*) molding clay. For Skinner, the use of this verb in Genesis 2:7–8 underscores God’s personal engagement with the material of creation. In the twentieth century, Victor Hamilton² advanced this understanding by demonstrating that *yatsar* also describes the work of a smith forging metal (Isa. 44:12), suggesting that divine formation encompasses a broader metaphor of craftsmanship. Kenneth Mathews³ interprets *yatsar* as an ‘anthropomorphic projection’ of divine intentionality, wherein God is not a distant architect but an artisan actively shaping existence. Gordon Wenham⁴ further highlights the artistic nuance of *yatsar*, contrasting it with the repetitive or mechanical labor implied by *asah* (‘to make’). These perspectives converge in portraying *yatsar* as the verb of divine intimacy, artistry, and purpose.

Linguistic and Philological Background of יָצַר

Etymologically, the root יָצַר belongs to a common Semitic family of words denoting shaping or forming. The Akkadian cognate *eṣēru* carries meanings such as ‘to draw, delineate, form,’ while in Ugaritic, the root *yṣr* appears in contexts related to fashioning and design.⁵ These parallels suggest that the Hebrew term *yatsar* developed within a shared ancient Near Eastern semantic field of craftsmanship. In Biblical Hebrew, the verb occurs primarily in the Qal stem, occasionally in the Niphal and Pual, and as a participle (יָצַר, ‘potter’). Its nominal derivatives, such as יָצָר (yetser, ‘formation’ or ‘inclination’),⁶ further extend the semantic field into anthropology and ethics (cf. Gen. 6:5; 8:21). The dual meaning of ‘formation’ and ‘inclination’ points to a profound theological insight: what God forms externally (creation), He also shapes internally (the human heart, as reference to reason, mind, emotion, as well as will or consciousness).

2 Victor P. Hamilton, *The Book of Genesis: Chapters 1–17*, The New International Commentary on the Old Testament (Grand Rapids, MI: Wm. B. Eerdmans, 1990), 156.

3 K. A. Mathews, *Genesis 1–11:26*, vol. 1A, The New American Commentary (Nashville: Broadman & Holman, 1996), 195.

4 Gordon J. Wenham, *Genesis 1–15*, vol. 1, Word Biblical Commentary (Dallas: Word, 1987), 59.

5 Francis Brown, S. R. Driver, and Charles A. Briggs, *The Brown-Driver-Briggs Hebrew and English Lexicon* (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1996), ref. 3335.

6 *Idem.*, ref. 3336.

Exegetical Analysis of יָצַר in the Old Testament

The verb *yatsar* appears sixty-three times throughout the Old Testament, distributed across narrative, poetic, and prophetic literature. Of these, thirty-five occurrences refer to divine action, and twenty-eight to human activity.⁷ This distribution itself is significant: the Hebrew Bible portrays God and humanity as sharing a linguistic and functional domain of formation, yet with vastly different moral and ontological implications.

Yatsar as divine action

Throughout the Old Testament, God is portrayed as shaping various aspects of creation, and one of the most fundamental is anthropological formation. In *Genesis 2:7*, ‘the LORD God formed (*yatsar*) man from the dust of the ground, establishing the foundational paradigm of human existence, and breathed into his nostrils the breath of life.’ Here, *yatsar* conveys not merely the act of assembling material substance but the intentional shaping of a being destined for relationship with its Creator. The text’s juxtaposition of dust and divine breath symbolizes the synthesis of material and spiritual dimensions.

Other passages, such as *Psalms 33:15*, show God forming the human heart, the center of moral and spiritual consciousness, while *Psalms 94:9* and *Psalms 139:16* highlight His role in shaping human senses and the span of life. In *Zechariah 12:1*, God is described as forming the human spirit (*ruach*), emphasizing the spiritual dimension of personhood. Thus, the divine act of “forming” expresses God’s comprehensive creative work in shaping not only the physical body but also the inner and spiritual nature of humanity.

In the Old Testament, God’s formative activity extends beyond humanity to encompass all realms of creation, history, and purpose. In biological and zoological formation, God is depicted as shaping the animal world, forming every creature of the field and the birds of the heavens (*Gen. 2:19*), and even exercising sovereignty over giant beings such as Leviathan (*Psalms 104:26*), symbolizing His power over chaos itself. In cosmological and geographical formation, God fashions the physi-

7 James Strong, *The Exhaustive Concordance of the Bible* (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1990), ref. 3335.

cal world – the dry land, mountains, and earth itself (Psalm. 95:5; Isa. 45:18; Amos 4:13), as well as the celestial and meteorological elements that sustain life, such as seasons (Psalm 74:17) and light (Isa. 45:7), demonstrating His comprehensive authority over creation.

Prophetic literature expands the semantic range of *yatsar*. In Isaiah 43:1, Yahweh declares, ‘I have created (*bara*) you, O Jacob; I have formed (*yatsar*) you, O Israel.’ The pairing of the two verbs underscores their complementarity: *bara* introduces existence; *yatsar* defines identity and purpose. Isaiah’s theology of creation thus unites ontology and teleology. Similarly, in Jeremiah 18:2-6, the potter metaphor embodies divine sovereignty and conditional judgment. The Lord reshapes nations as a potter reworks clay – a dynamic image of both mercy and discipline.

Moving into historical and political formation, the divine act of *yatsar* encompasses the orchestration of world events: the Assyrian invasion (2 Kgs. 19:25; Isa. 37:26), the rise of Cyrus and the Persian empire (Isa. 46:11), and other historical developments (Isa. 22:11; Jer. 33:2) are all presented as outcomes of divine design. Similarly, in corporate and national formation, Israel’s identity is portrayed as the result of God’s formative will—He “formed” Israel as His covenant people (Isa. 43:1,21; 44:2,21,24; 45:11), not through natural processes but through divine intentionality, mirroring the creation of *ha’adam* in Genesis 2.

In soteriological and eschatological formation, Isaiah 49:5 presents the Servant of the Lord as one “formed from the womb” for a redemptive mission, foreshadowing, in Christian interpretation, the incarnation – where divine formation occurs within human existence, linking creation to salvation. The concept also extends to instruments of divine judgment, as seen in Jeremiah 18:11 and Amos 7:1, where even calamity and locust plagues are “formed” by God to accomplish justice. Finally, comprehensive universal formation finds its expression in Jeremiah 10:16 and 51:19, which proclaim YHWH as “the one who formed all things” (*yotser hakkol*). This declaration culminates the theology of *yatsar*, portraying God’s creative sovereignty as absolute – embracing the totality of space, time, matter, history, and destiny under His purposeful design.

***Yatsar* as human action**

When human beings serve as the subject of *yatsar* (יצר, “to form” or “to shape”), the verb consistently describes the fashioning of tangible objects

through manual craftsmanship, though it occasionally extends to abstract moral realities. The primary objects of human *yatsar* include idols (Exod. 32:4; Isa. 44:9-10; Hab. 2:18), reflecting humanity’s misguided attempt to shape divine representations from material substances. The verb also describes the potter’s craft in forming clay vessels for various domestic and ceremonial uses (2 Sam. 17:28; Ps. 2:9; Isa. 29:16; 30:14; Jer. 18:2-4), establishing *yatsar* as the technical term for ceramic production. Additionally, craftsmen shape tools for work (Isa. 44:12), demonstrating the verb’s application to metallurgy and general artisanal activity. Notably, Psalm 94:20 employs *yatsar* metaphorically to describe the shaping of evil, lawlessness, or misfortune, suggesting that human forming activity extends beyond physical objects to include the deliberate construction of moral wickedness and social injustice. This semantic range reveals that while human *yatsar* primarily denotes material craftsmanship – particularly the potter’s work – it also encompasses humanity’s capacity to “shape” both religious error through idolatry and moral corruption through unjust decrees.

Theological Implications

The theology of *yatsar* has wide-ranging implications for the doctrine of creation and divine providence. First, it affirms that the world is not a product of arbitrary power but of intentional design. God’s creative act is both rational and relational; He forms with wisdom and for purpose. Second, the verb reveals the continuity between creation and moral formation. The same God who formed the human body also shapes the human heart and historical destiny. Third, *yatsar* implies divine immanence: the Creator remains intimately involved with His creation, continuously shaping events, individuals, and communities. Conversely, the human use of *yatsar* exposes the distortions of creativity under sin. Humanity shapes idols (Exod. 32:4; Isa. 44:9–10) and devises wickedness (Ps. 94:20). The same capacity for formation, when detached from divine wisdom, becomes destructive. This tension underlies the Old Testament’s anthropology: humanity mirrors divine creativity but requires divine guidance to use it rightly.

Semantic Analysis of *Bara’* (אַרַב) in the Old Testament

The Hebrew verb *bara’* (אַרַב) appears 55 times throughout the Old Testament, exhibiting a distinctive distribution pattern that reveals its

predominantly theological character. Of these occurrences, God is the subject in 50 instances (91%), while human agents account for only 5 occurrences (9%).⁸ This statistical asymmetry suggests that *bara'* functions primarily as a verb of divine creative activity within biblical Hebrew.

Divine Creative Activity: Objects of *Bara'*

When God serves as the subject of *bara'*, the verb encompasses a remarkably diverse range of created objects, extending far beyond physical matter to include abstract concepts, moral realities, and temporal dimensions.

Cosmological and Physical Creation

The most fundamental use of *bara'* appears in *Genesis 1:1,21,27* and *2:3*, where God creates the heavens and the earth – establishing space, matter, living organisms, and time itself. This foundational act encompasses the totality of physical reality and sets the temporal framework within which all subsequent events unfold.

Beyond the initial cosmic order, *bara'* describes God's creation of humanity and the institution of the family (*Gen. 1:27; 5:1-2*), marking human beings as a distinct category of created existence. The verb also extends to natural phenomena, including the creation of light and darkness, peace and calamity (*Isa. 45:7*), demonstrating divine sovereignty over both beneficial and adverse conditions.

Unique and Unprecedented Acts

Bara' frequently designates divine actions that are entirely novel or unprecedented. *Exodus 34:10* and *Numbers 16:30* employ the verb to describe wonders and unique events “that have never been done before,” emphasizing God's capacity to transcend natural patterns and established orders. This semantic dimension underscores the verb's association with innovation and the introduction of genuinely new realities into existence.

Spiritual and Moral Transformation

The semantic range of *bara'* extends significantly into the realm of spiritual renewal and moral transformation. *Psalm 51:10* employs the

⁸ James Strong, *The Exhaustive Concordance of the Bible* (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1990), ref. 1254.

verb in David’s plea for God to create “a new heart” within him, indicating that divine creative power operates not only in the physical realm but also in the internal, spiritual dimension of human existence. Similarly, God creates righteousness, salvation, and deliverance (Isa. 45:8), suggesting that even abstract moral realities and salvific events fall within the scope of divine *bara’*.

Spatial and Conceptual Order

In Psalm 89:12, *bara’* describes God’s creation of order and orientation, specifically mentioning the north and south. This usage reflects ancient Near Eastern cosmological thought, wherein the north symbolized the hidden and the realm of darkness, while the south represented the revealed and the kingdom of light. The reference to Tabor (west) and Horeb (east) further illustrates how *bara’* establishes not merely physical directions but meaningful spatial organization imbued with theological significance.

Prophetic and Eschatological Creation

The prophetic literature demonstrates an expansion of *bara’* into eschatological contexts. Isaiah employs the verb to describe God’s creation of a people (Isa. 43:1, 7, 15), a shelter of cloud and light (Isa. 4:5), and praise on the lips of humanity (Isa. 57:19). Most dramatically, *bara’* appears in visions of cosmic renewal: the creation of new heavens and a new earth (Isa. 65:17) and things that bring everlasting joy (Isa. 65:18). The verb also describes the creation of new historical events (Isa. 48:7) and unprecedented realities (Jer. 31:22), indicating its function in describing God’s ongoing creative engagement with history and future redemption.

Human Action: The Semantic Shift of *Bara’*

The five instances where *bara’* takes a human subject reveal a significant semantic shift from divine creation to mundane, physical actions. In these contexts, the verb loses its theological connotations and instead denotes: 1) **Cutting or hewing** (Ezek. 23:47) – referring to violent action with sharp implements; 2) **Cutting down or clearing** (Josh. 17:15,18) – describing the clearing of forested areas; and 3) **Feeding or fattening** (1 Sam. 2:29; 2 Sam. 12:17) – indicating the act of nourishing or making fat.

This semantic divergence is remarkable: when human beings are the subject, *bara'* abandons any connotation of creative innovation or bringing something into existence *ex nihilo* or even *ex materia*. Instead, it describes destructive actions (cutting, clearing) or sustaining actions (feeding). This linguistic phenomenon suggests that biblical Hebrew reserves the creative theological meaning of *bara'* exclusively for divine agency, while permitting the same verbal root to carry entirely different meanings when applied to human activity.

Theological Implications

The statistical and semantic analysis of *bara'* reveals several important theological principles. First, the overwhelming predominance of divine subjects (91%) establishes *bara'* as primarily a theological term describing God's unique creative power. Second, the extraordinary breadth of objects created through *bara'* – from cosmic structures to moral realities, from physical matter to spiritual transformation – indicates that divine creativity transcends categorical boundaries. Third, the semantic shift when humans become the subject effectively creates a linguistic barrier that protects the uniqueness of divine creative action. Human “creating” (*bara'*) involves manipulation, destruction, or sustenance of existing materials, never the bringing forth of genuine novelty or the establishment of foundational order characteristic of divine *bara'*.

This semantic structure embedded within biblical Hebrew itself thus functions as a theological commentary, affirming through linguistic convention the distinction between Creator and creature, and reserving for God alone the capacity to create in the fullest sense of the term.

Discussion: *Bara'* and *Yatsar* as Complementary Divine Actions

The verbs *yatsar* and *bara'* are distinct yet complementary expressions of divine creativity.⁹ The first emphasizes divine wisdom and engagement; the second, divine power and transcendence. *Bara'* appears fifty-five times

9 For a clearer visualization of the comparison between the two terms, see Tables 1 and 2.

in the Old Testament, nearly always with God as the subject, and denotes creation that transcends natural causation. *Yatsar*, in contrast, implies formation within creation—a process of ordering, organizing, and personal shaping. While *bara'* answers the question ‘What does God create?’, *yatsar* answers ‘How and why does God create?’ Theologically, this distinction mirrors the twofold character of divine agency: transcendent causation and immanent formation. This complementarity is particularly evident in *Isaiah 45:7*, where God declares, ‘I make (*yatsar*) light and create (*bara'*) darkness; I make weal and create woe.’¹⁰ Here, *yatsar* applies to light – an element of order, regularity, and structure – while *bara'* applies to darkness, symbolizing the mysterious and uncontainable aspects of creation. The verse thus reflects the balance of divine artistry and sovereignty. This complementary relationship suggests that biblical creation theology requires both verbs to convey the fullness of divine creative action: the power to initiate existence (*bara'*) and the wisdom to shape it according to purpose (*yatsar*).

When these verbs describe human action, however, a striking moral ambivalence emerges. Both *bara'* and *yatsar* can express useful and necessary human activities – *bara'* describing feeding or clearing forests for habitation, *yatsar* denoting the shaping of vessels and tools – yet both also encompass physically, morally, and spiritually destructive behaviors. Human *bara'* can signify greedy fattening through exploitation of sacred offerings, while human *yatsar* includes the fashioning of idols and the devising of evil and wicked schemes. This dual capacity reflects humanity’s fundamental ambiguity as a creative agent: capable of constructive craftsmanship yet prone to perversion of that creative power.

The theological contrast becomes even sharper when examining the outcomes of divine versus human shaping. Everything that God shapes (*yatsar*) is beautiful, ennobling, and endures forever, reflecting the eternal wisdom and goodness inherent in divine creative purpose. By contrast, what humanity shapes most often degenerates into means of idolatry and moral regression, revealing the corrupting influence of human self-interest and autonomy from divine guidance. This pattern points to a fundamental principle: creative power divorced from divine wisdom inevitably tends toward destruction rather than flourishing.

10 Accordind to the NRSV version.

Table 1: *Comparison between bara'and yatsar as divine action*

Bara'as an action of God	Yatsar as an action of God
The heavens and the earth: space, matter, life (living things) and time (Gen. 1:1,21,27; 2:3);	Everything (space, time, and events) - (Jer. 10:16; 51:19); animals and birds (Gen. 2:19; Psa. 104:26);
Man and the family (Gen. 1:27; 5:1,2);	The man / the human beings (Gen 2:7,8); the eyes of man (Psa. 94:9);
Unique things (that have never been done before), wonders (Exod. 34:10; Num. 16:30); Events (Isa. 48:7); New things (Jer. 31:22). New heavens and a new earth (Isa. 65:17);	Historical events (2 Kings 19:25; Isa. 22:11; 37:26; 46:11; Jer. 33:2);
A new heart (Ps. 51:10);	The heart of man (Psa. 33:15);
Order, orientation (Ps. 89:12);	The seasons (Psa. 74:17);
A shelter of cloud and light (Is. 4:5); Light and darkness, peace and trouble (Isa. 45:7);	Light (Isa. 45:7);
A people (Isa. 43:1,7; 43:15);	A people / Israel (Isa. 27:11; 43:1,21; 44:2,21,24; 45:11);
Righteousness, salvation and deliverance (Isa. 45:8);	The days of man (Psa. 139:16); The Servant of the Lord (Isa. 49:5) – incarnation?!?
Praise on the lips of men (Isa. 57:19); Things that bring everlasting joy (Isa. 65:18);	The spirit of man (Zech. 12:1); Instruments of punishment / Punishment (Jer. 18:11; Amos 7:1)

Table 2: Comparison between *bara'* and *yatsar* as human action

<i>Bara'</i> as an action of man	<i>Yatsar</i> as an action of man
cutting (Ezek. 23:47),	To shape idols (Exod. 32:4; Is. 44:9,10; Hab. 2:18);
cutting down or clearing (Josh. 17:15,18),	To shape clay vessels for various uses (2 Sam. 17:28; Ps. 2:9; Is. 29:16; 30:14; Jer. 18:2-4);
Fattening / feeding (1 Sam. 2:29; 2 Sam. 12:17).	To form tools for work (Is. 44:12);
	To shape evil, lawlessness (misfortune / wickedness) (Ps. 94:20).

Conclusion

The analysis of *yatsar* (יָצַר) reveals a theology of formation that complements and deepens the biblical doctrine of creation. While *bara'* (בָּרָא) denotes God's transcendent power to call forth existence, *yatsar* articulates His immanent engagement in shaping, organizing, and sustaining the created order. Together, they portray a Creator who is both omnipotent and intimately present, whose creative acts are characterized by both might and artistry. The study of *yatsar* thus underscores a vision of creation as a continuous, relational process – one that extends from cosmic formation to personal and moral transformation. In contrast, human formation apart from divine guidance leads to idolatry, injustice, and chaos. The biblical theology of *yatsar* therefore calls for an alignment of human creativity with divine wisdom.

Significantly, the concept of humanity being shaped (*yatsar*) according to the image of God (*tselem Elohim*) establishes the theological foundation for freedom of conscience, which in turn becomes the cornerstone of human rights, education, and peace. If human beings are shaped by divine wisdom for a specific purpose – to reflect God's image – then the human conscience represents that interior capacity to discern moral truth and respond to divine purpose. Freedom of conscience, therefore, is not merely a political concession but a recognition of humanity's fundamental nature

as beings shaped for relationship with transcendent truth. This freedom becomes the essential prerequisite for authentic human rights, as rights derive their ultimate justification not from state authority or social contract alone, but from the inherent dignity of beings formed in the divine image. Similarly, genuine education must respect this freedom of conscience, cultivating rather than coercing the individual's capacity for moral discernment and wise judgment – mirroring the divine *yatsar* that shapes with purpose rather than manipulates with force. Finally, lasting peace requires the mutual recognition of this shared dignity: that all human beings, regardless of culture or creed, are shaped according to the same divine image and possess the same sacred freedom to seek truth according to conscience.

References:

- ✦ BROWN, Francis, DRIVER, Samuel R. și BRIGGS, Charles A., *The Enhanced Brown-Driver-Briggs Hebrew and English Lexicon of the Old Testament*, Snowball Publishing, Chicago: MI, 2010.
- ✦ BROWN, Francis, DRIVER, S.R., BRIGGS, Charles, A., *Brown-Driver-Briggs Hebrew and English Lexicon*, Unabridged, Electronic Database, (2006): BibleSoft, Inc. <https://www.studydrive.org/lexicons/hebrew>.
- ✦ DE BURGH, William, *The Englishman's Hebrew and Chaldee Concordance of the Old Testament*, Samuel Bagster and Sons, London, vol. 2, 1866.
- ✦ ELWELL, W.A. și COMFORT, P.W. (ed.), *Tyndale Bible dictionary*, Wheaton, IL: Tyndale House Publishers, 2001.
- ✦ FREEDMAN, D.N. (ed.), *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, Doubleday, New York: NY, vol. 3, 1996.
- ✦ GORDON, Cyrus H., *Ugaritic Textbook: Grammar, Text in Transliteration, Cuneiform Selections, Glossary, Indices*, Editrice Pontificio Instituto Biblico Roma, Revised Reprint, 1998.
- ✦ HAMILTON, Victor P. *The Book of Genesis: Chapters 1–17*. The New International Commentary on the Old Testament. Grand Rapids, MI: Wm. B. Eerdmans, 1990.
- ✦ HARKAVY, Alexander, *Students' Hebrew and Chaldee Dictionary to the Old Testament*, Hebrew Publishing Co., New York, 1914.
- ✦ HAYES, J.H. (ed.), *Dictionary of Biblical Interpretation*, Abingdon, Nashville: TN, 1999.

- ✦ JENNI, Ernst și WESTERMANN, Claus, *Theological Lexicon of the Old Testament*, trad. Mark E. Biddle, 3 vols., Hendrickson Publishers, Peabody, Massachusetts, vol. 2, 1997.
- ✦ KÖHLER, Ludwig și BAUMGARTNER, Walter și STAMM, Johann J, *The Hebrew and Aramaic Lexicon of the Old Testament*. Traducere și editare sub supervizarea lui RICHARDSON, M.E.J., 5 vols., Brill, Leiden, 1994-2000.
- ✦ MATHEWS, K. A. *Genesis 1–11:26*. Vol. 1A. The New American Commentary. Nashville: Broadman & Holman, 1996.
- ✦ SKINNER, John. *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on Genesis*. International Critical Commentary. New York: Scribner, 1910.
- ✦ STRONG, James. *The Exhaustive Concordance of the Bible*. Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1990.
- ✦ WENHAM, Gordon J. *Genesis 1–15*. Vol. 1. Word Biblical Commentary. Dallas: Word, 1987.

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